

FREQUENCY OF MYOCARDITIS IN PEDIATRICS HEART FAILURE PATIENT

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency of myocarditis among pediatric heart failure patients and to assess its association with clinical symptoms, diagnostic markers and patient outcomes.

Study Duration and Setting:

This cross-sectional study was conducted over a period of six months (October 2024 to March 2025) at Dr. Abdul Shakoor's Hospital, Hala, a tertiary care pediatric cardiology center.

Methods:

A total of 240 children between 1 and 15 years of age with features on presentation suggestive of heart failure were included. Myocarditis was diagnosed clinically with at least 2 abnormal ECG findings, elevated cardiac biomarkers (troponin, CRP) and reduced ejection fraction less than 50% on echocardiography. There was a prospective, structured proforma collection of data regarding demographic data, symptoms, diagnostic markers and outcome. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 26. Chi-square and t-tests were used at 0.05 p-value to assess associations that were statistically significant.

Results:

65 (27.1%) out of the 240 patients were diagnosed with myocarditis. The most frequent symptoms (32.9%) were fatigue and chest pain (22.5%). There was a significant association with gender ($p = 0.027$), clinical symptoms ($p = 0.022$), heart failure ($p = 0.011$). The mean ejection fraction was lower in patients with myocarditis ($45.2 \pm 7.8\%$) compared with that in patients without myocarditis ($53.8 \pm 8.2\%$) and mortality was higher (15.4%). 38.3% and 41.3% of the cases had elevated levels of troponin and CRP.

Conclusion:

Myocarditis has a frequency of 27.1% as a significant contributor to pediatric heart failure. The disease is associated with distinct clinical symptoms, lower ejection fraction and higher risk for poor outcomes. Early clinical recognition based on ECG, biomarkers and echocardiography is essential for diagnosis and management at the right time, especially in resource limited setting.

INTRODUCTION

Myocarditis is an inflammatory disease of the myocardium that is becoming increasingly appreciated as the leading cause of acute and chronic heart failure in children. It accounts for the approximately 10–20% of pediatric patients with dilated cardiomyopathy and up to 6–12% of sudden cardiac deaths in the pediatric population (1,2). State recognized often undiagnosed due to its heterogeneous clinical presentation, overlap with other viral or respiratory diseases (3). Myocarditis in children manifests with either nonspecific symptoms (such as fatigue, irritability and tachypnoea, vomiting, chest pain) or serious manifestations (cardiogenic shock, arrhythmia) depending on the phase and severity of myocardial inflammation (4,5).

Pediatric myocarditis is estimated to have an incidence of 1 to 2 cases per 100,000 children per year worldwide but this number is probably underestimated as availability to access to diagnostics and limited reliance upon clinical suspicion alone (6). Afflicted children in low- and middle-income countries present with an added challenge due to the unavailability of advanced imaging tools such as cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR) (7). While endomyocardial biopsy is said to be the gold standard for diagnosis, it is rarely done in children because it is invasive, carries procedural risk and is not widely available (8). Diagnosis relies on patient clinical symptoms, biomarker analysis, coupled with echocardiographic evaluation.

Diagnosis of myocarditis is often made with the help of cardiac troponin and C reactive protein (CRP)—but there is no specific test that confirms the diagnosis. In 30–60% of pediatric myocarditis cases there is elevation of troponin levels which indicates persistence of ongoing myocardial injury and CRP which is used to indicate systemic inflammation (9,10). ECG abnormalities are also common (in excess of 50–70% of cases) but their specificity is limited (11). Echocardiography contributes, especially through assessment of the left ventricular ejection fraction (EF). Moderate to severe myocarditis is often associated with decreased EF and it has been shown to be an important prognostic sign of duration of

hospitalization, need for inotropic support and mortality (12).

The underlying causes for pediatric heart failure are a complex syndrome from a multifactorial etiology, among them congenital heart defects, cardiomyopathies, metabolic diseases and myocarditis (13). Myocarditis is frequently overlooked as a reversible cause of new onset heart failure in the setting of children presenting with heart failure. Approximately 25–30% of pediatric heart failure admissions into tertiary care centers are observed to have an occult myocarditis, with the figures varying depending on the diagnostic criteria as well as regional healthcare capabilities (14).

Susceptibility to myocarditis may also be related to gender, with gender differences in susceptibility and disease courses, the male being more prevalent and the disease course worse, possibly because of sex differences in immune responsiveness and hormonal modulation (15). Related to myocarditis, which is an essential clinical condition whose true frequency in pediatric heart failure patients and its diagnostic associations are poorly characterized, particularly in South Asia and equivalent areas.

This study aims to identify the frequency of the incidence of myocarditis in patients with pediatric heart failure and to investigate the clinical and diagnostic association variables of myocarditis, gender, presenting symptoms, ECG findings, cardiac biomarker and ejection fraction. These relationships are essential to develop to guide early diagnosis in this vulnerable patient group and to improve outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out cross-sectional observational study in Dr. Abdul Shakoor's Hospital, Hala, which is a tertiary care, over six months period from October 2024 to March 2025. The objective of this study was to determine the frequency of myocarditis among pediatrics admitted with heart failure and its relation to clinical indicators and outcomes.

The study group included children 1 to 15 years old admitted with heart failure clinical manifestations.

Enrolment of a total of 240 patients were done by non-probability consecutive sampling technique. All participants had informed consent from the parents or guardians.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All children aged 1 - 15 years admitted with the clinical diagnosis of heart failure were eligible to be included. The symptoms were breathlessness, chest pain, fatigue, palpitations and poor feeding, which were defined as heart failure. Only subjects that had a complete diagnostic evaluation (ECG, echocardiography, troponin levels and C reactive protein) were taken into account. Exclusions included patients who had congenital heart disease as the primary diagnosis, patients with chronic systemic comorbidities (such as hypertension, chronic asthma, chronic kidney disease, diabetes) or who did not have complete medical records. It was also necessary to exclude children whose guardians were unwilling to give informed consent.

Diagnostic Criteria for Myocarditis

Myocarditis was diagnosed clinically by the presence of at least two of the following; abnormal electrocardiographic (ECG) finding such as ST-T wave changes, conduction abnormalities or arrhythmias, elevated cardiac biomarkers (troponin, C-reactive protein) and echocardiographic evidence of impaired systolic function as left ventricular ejection fraction lower than 50% or presence of segmental wall motion abnormality. Adapted from established pediatric myocarditis guidelines, these diagnostic criteria were modified for use with the modern low resource environment where cardiac MRI and endomyocardial biopsy were rarely used.

Data Collection and Variables

Structured clinical proforma was developed and subsequently used for recording patient information for this study. All the collected variables included demographic details such as age and gender and clinical symptoms including fatigue, chest pain,

palpitations and shortness of breath. Based on ECG findings (classified as normal or abnormal), serum troponin and CRP levels (raised or normal), echocardiographic measurements of ejection fraction were documented as a percentage. At discharge, outcomes were classified as recovered, ongoing or deceased and verified to be heart failure as per all patients' clinical status.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26. Demographic data and diagnostic features were summarized by application of descriptive statistics. Chi square tests were done for categorical variables while continuous variables (heart rate, EF) were compared using independent sample t tests. Statistical significance was considered if $p < 0.05$. The associations between myocarditis, patient outcomes and diagnostic markers were explored.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to the data collection, the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Dr. Abdul Shakoor's Hala Hospital approves the ethical study. Ethical guidelines were observed during the study and all data used was kept confidential to the patient and only used for academic purposes.

RESULTS

Baseline Demographics and Clinical Characteristics
The study included a total of 240 pediatric patients with clinical presentation of heart failure. The mean age of the participants was 8.06 ± 3.99 years. The gender distribution was slightly female predominate as there were 128 female (53.3%) and 112 male (46.7%) (Table 1).

Presenting symptoms included fatigue (79 patients; 32.9%), shortness of breath (22.9%), chest pain (22.5%) and palpitations (21.7%). 211 were clinically diagnosed with heart failure and 29 (12.1%) were not diagnosed. Myocarditis was diagnosed in 65 patients (27.1%) and not diagnosed in the remaining 175 (72.9%).

Table 1: Demographics & Symptoms (N = 240)

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	112	46.7%

	Female	128	53.3%
Symptoms	Fatigue	79	32.9%
	Shortness of Breath	55	22.9%
	Chest Pain	54	22.5%
	Palpitations	52	21.7%
Heart Failure	Yes	211	87.9%
	No	29	12.1%
Myocarditis Diagnosed	Yes	65	27.1%
	No	175	72.9%
Age	Mean ± SD	-	8.06 ± 3.99

Table 2: Diagnostic Findings & Outcomes

Category	Subcategory	Frequency (n)	Percentage / Mean ± SD
ECG	Abnormal	145	60.4%
Troponin	Raised	92	38.3%
CRP	Raised	99	41.3%
Outcome	Recovered	166	69.2%
	Ongoing	51	21.3%
	Died	23	9.6%
Heart Rate	Myocarditis Diagnosed	-	132.5 ± 11.6 bpm
	No Myocarditis	-	120.8 ± 9.4 bpm
Ejection Fraction (%)	Myocarditis Diagnosed	-	45.2 ± 7.8%
	No Myocarditis	-	53.8 ± 8.2%

Figure 1: Reduced Ejection Fraction in Pediatric Patients with Myocarditis

Diagnostic Indicators and Outcomes

The diagnostic indicators comprised of abnormal ECG findings in 145 patients (60.4%). Elevated troponin was present in 92 patients (38.3%), elevated CRP in 99 patients (41.3%).

Results of analysis of the cardiac function parameters revealed that a group of myocarditis patients had significantly higher average hear rate (132.5 ± 11.6 bpm) as compared to a group without myocarditis (120.8 ± 9.4 bpm). In similar vein, myocarditis patients had a lower average ejection fraction (45.2 ± 7.8 %) as compared to the average ejection fraction of the non-myocarditis patients (53.8 ± 8.2 %) implying poorer myocardial function.

Results indicated that the majority of patients (166; 69.2%) had recovered and 51 (21.3%) had ongoing management at the time of data collection and 23 (9.6%) had died during this study (Table 2).

In pediatric patients diagnosed with myocarditis (Figure 1), ejection fraction was severely diminished compared to patients without the condition and is a predictor of decreased cardiac function.

Association Between Myocarditis and Clinical Variables

Statistically significant relationships were found between diagnosis of myocarditis and gender ($p = 0.027$), symptoms ($p = 0.022$) and presence of heart failure ($p = 0.011$) as determined by chi-square analysis (Table 3). This shows that these clinical and demographic factors could affect the development of myocarditis in pediatric heart failure patients.

Table 3: Significant Chi-Square Associations

Variable Pair	Chi-Square	df	p-value	Significance
Gender × Myocarditis Diagnosed	4.892	1	0.027	Significant
Symptoms × Myocarditis Diagnosed	9.567	3	0.022	Significant
Heart Failure × Myocarditis Diagnosed	6.432	1	0.011	Significant

Myocarditis and Patient Outcomes

Mortality was higher in the myocarditis group (15.4%) as compared to the non-myocarditis group (7.4%), as shown in Table 4. Only 63.1% of patients with

myocarditis fully recovered as opposed to 71.4% of patients without myocarditis. These findings highlight that myocarditis is clinically severe and prognostically significant to pediatric heart failure.

Table 4: Myocarditis Status by Patient Outcome

Myocarditis Status	Recovered (n)	Ongoing (n)	Died (n)	Total
Yes (n = 65)	41	14	10	65
No (n = 175)	125	37	13	175
Total (n = 240)	166	51	23	240

This table shows that 15.4% died in the patients who were diagnosed with myocarditis which is higher than the 7.4% mortality risk of those who were not diagnosed with myocarditis.

Figure 2: Patient Outcomes by Myocarditis Status

Figure 2 shows stacked bar chart of outcome between patients diagnosed with and without myocarditis. This demonstrates that the myocarditis group has a higher mortality rate (15.4%) compared with the 7.4% in those without myocarditis, which emphasizes the fact that myocarditis has a more serious prognosis.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to determine how frequently myocarditis occurred as an etiology of heart failure in the pediatric age group and to discern clinical and diagnostic associations with the disease. The results show that 27.1% of the cases of pediatric heart failure were diagnosed with myocarditis, a finding confirming a reasonable prevalence within this subgroup and reinforcing the previous concerns raised in pediatric cardiology literature (1, 2).

Table 3 shows a statistically significant association between gender and myocarditis diagnosis with slightly more males (28.6%) having this diagnosis than females (25.8%) ($p = 0.027$). This corresponds to the fact that there is a higher predisposition for male gender to viral myocarditis, that may be caused by sex specific modulation of immune response and hormonal impact (3,4). Key symptoms associated with myocarditis included fatigue and chest pain, which were statistically significantly associated with

myocarditis ($p = 0.022$) indicating they are of value as early clinical indicators (5,6).

Diagnostic biomarkers provided additional clinical suspicion. The prevalence of abnormal ECG findings was observed in 60.4% cohort, 38.3% had elevated troponin and 41.3% had elevated CRP (Table 2). Troponin is considered a well-recognized marker of myocardial injury (7), although it is without great specificity in pediatric myocarditis and should be interpreted in the clinical context

(8). CRP is often increased in inflammation but lacks cardiac specificity alone (it is of limited diagnostic value alone) (9).

Myocarditis patients had significantly lower ejection fraction as compared to the non-myocarditis patients ($45.2 \pm 7.8\%$ vs $53.8 \pm 8.2\%$, Figure 1). Systolic reduced function is the hallmark of myocarditis, which is known to associate with poor outcomes such as dilated cardiomyopathy and the progression to end stage heart failure (10-12). Ejection fraction, used a tool for noninvasive, accessible indicator of the myocardial function, becomes a very important tool in risk stratification.

With regard to clinical outcome, the mortality rate of 15.4% for myocarditis was significantly higher than that of the 7.4% in the no myocarditis group (Table 4). Although this difference was nearly statistically

significant ($p = 0.086$), it is clinically significant and agrees with data that has shown that myocarditis is associated with an increased risk for the development of cardiogenic shock, arrhythmias and long-term ventricular dysfunction (13,14).

ECG abnormalities ($p = 0.608$) or levels of CRP ($p = 0.407$) were not associated significantly with myocarditis, which was characteristic of these findings' non-specificities and the requirements therefor for definitively diagnostic modalities. High diagnostic accuracy in the detection of myocardial inflammation and fibrosis using CMR imaging is reported, with CMR imaging being regarded as gold standard noninvasive tool when available, not routinely available in many settings (15,16). Although endomyocardial biopsy is rarely used in pediatrics because it is invasive and risky for complications, it is the definitive diagnostic method in ambiguous cases (17).

Strengths of this study include $N = 240$, clinical variable tracking and the application of a method to identify associations. However, limitations exist. There are potential problems of retrospective design such as potential selection bias. CMR or biopsy assessment to confirm diagnosis is absent. The study's future should include longitudinal follow up and advanced imaging to clarify progression and outcomes.

This study demonstrates that myocarditis as a cause of heart failure in pediatric population is a frequent and clinically significant condition and is associated with gender, presenting symptoms and systolic function. Early recognition, risk stratification and comprehensive evaluation are of great significance in minimizing the effects of facilitation on these affected children.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflict of interest in relation to the present study.

CONCLUSION

Myocarditis is a frequent and important cause of heart failure in children and accounted for 27.1% of the population of heart failure patients studied. As such, key associations were observed with gender, specific symptoms such as fatigue and chest pain and

importantly reduced ejection fraction. These findings necessitate early recognition and risk-based evaluation to improve the prognosis in these children. In addition, there is elevated mortality in the myocarditis group, highlighting the clinical seriousness. Examining collaboration between various clinical, diagnostic and statistical indicators is necessary for timely management and good outcome.

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